

COLLECTING IN TURKESTAN

Work of Botanical Explorer Hindered By Many Difficulties and Even Dangers—
Wild Vegetation Scarce and Flora Not Rich—Native Fruits of Mediocre
Quality But Extremely Hardy and Resistant to Drought and Alkali.¹

FRANK N. MEYER,

Agricultural Explorer, Office of Foreign Seed and Plant Introduction, Bureau of
Plant Industry, U. S. Department of Agriculture, Washington, D. C.

TASHKENT, TURKESTAN.

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ALL this delay is, as you surely will feel with me, of very great annoyance and becomes really depressing. There are moments when the loneliness of this exploration work becomes too great and I would like to fly off to regions where I could find more intellectual and social surroundings. And I have such a long journey yet ahead of me. Great Scott! before I appear somewhere in Eastern China, I'll have gone through many a lonesome day! That's one of the troubles connected with exploration in out-of-the-way places; this loneliness and this great waste of valuable time and energy. Of course it could be worse yet. Polar expeditions are still way ahead of our work in waste of all sorts of things.

As I wrote you from Samarkand on July 4, 1910, I had engaged a guide and had had an interpreter already for a few days. We had seen the police about our trip and the chief had said everything was O. K., but in Pendshikent we would have to get a paper from the police there.

On Tuesday, July 5, we had negotiations with various horsemen and cart-

people and as we were assured that in Pendshikent we would be able to get cheaper and better horses, we went by a large cart to that last named city on the next day, where we arrived after a hard ride at ten o'clock in the evening of that same day.

A PLAGUE OF LOCUSTS.

On Thursday, July 7, we inspected the grain market and seed stores, where I bought some samples of various things and in the afternoon we had conferences with the police and with horse men. I got a paper from the acting chief of police and on Friday, July 8, we left Pendshikent. We travelled first through a dry, elevated plain, where scanty growth of wheat, barley, linseed and rape was to be seen, while tens of thousands of locusts were devouring whatever they could find. In the afternoon we went through some gullies and passes and then mountain climbing had begun. On a few places we saw some beautiful *Eremurus* and yellow larkspurs, but in general the mountains were devoid of vegetation, save some *Astragalus* and a *Capparis spinosa* and some *Artemisias*. At 9 P. M. we stopped at last in a town called Stood, about 5,000 feet above sea level. We slept on the porch of the Muhammadan temple and got but little

¹The story of Mr. Meyer's entry to Turkestan was told in the March issue of *The Journal of Heredity*; the continuation of it, as told in letters to his chief, is given herewith. The accompanying photographs are all by Mr. Meyer: the scientific names are in the form used by him, and not necessarily in the form adopted by the department, when the material was distributed to plant breeders in the United States. Mr. Meyer's exploration of Turkestan resulted, as most plant breeders know, in the introduction to the United States of many tons of material, including hundreds of species of plants suited to desert climates, which are being tested in the southwestern United States. His collection of alfalfas was perhaps the most valuable single contribution. Mr. Meyer is now engaged in a three-year exploration of eastern China, where he has already made important discoveries of chestnuts, jujubes and persimmons.—THE EDITOR.

THE VALUABLE KARAGATCH TREE.

This dense-headed, desert shade tree (*Ulmus campestris umbraculifera*) is found throughout Russian and Chinese Turkestan, although the forms in the two countries are distinct, according to Meyer. The photograph shows a particularly beautiful specimen at Orono, in the province of Samarkand, Russian Turkestan, July 13, 1910. It has been introduced to the United States, and promises to be extremely valuable in the arid Southwest. (Figure 4.)

supper that night, it being too late to find anything.

On Saturday, July 9, I went around for several hours in the mountains, collecting seeds and herbarium material and at noon we left with our little caravan of six horses and six men (interpreter, guide, three horsemen and myself). We passed through a wild, mountain valley, where a roaring torrent was still eating out its bed deeper and deeper; after having scaled a dangerous, dry mountain, we arrived at sunset at a beautiful but cold lake at 10,000 feet altitude; this lake is called Kalikulan and is fed from the eternal snows on the mountains around. The water was so cold that one wouldn't readily bathe in it, and as for drinking, one could only take a mouthful at the time. The soil in these high regions is sterile and the

growing season very short, for the snow melts away in early May and returns again at the beginning of September. Still one finds there masses of Junipers (*Juniperus foetidissima*), Barberries, bush honeysuckles (*Lonicera sp.*), yellow roses (*Rosa xanthina*), a mountain ash (*Sorbus thianshanica*), besides various herbaceous plants like *Eremurus sp.*, *Gentiana verna*, *Leonurus (?)*, several Compositae, etc. We were lucky enough to find at the lake an encampment of a local Sart administrator and slept that night in a tent made of carpets, but still it was cold, after coming in two days from the hot plains.

SCARCITY OF FOOD.

On Sunday, July 10, we left our lovely, silent sheet of water and climbed over one high and difficult mountain, where

NATIVE PLUM IN FULL BLOOM.

Russian Asia is rich in native plums, some of which are valuable commercially, while others are promising only as hardy stocks for grafting. *Prunus insilitia*, shown in this picture, is locally known as the alutcha, and is said to be extraordinarily prolific, as well as a regular bearer. Some of the species are quite ornamental. Meyer mentions one found along a watercourse in the mountains near Kulikalan, Samarkand, Turkestan, at an elevation of 6,000 feet, which had light green leaves and bore long racemes of small, oval, scarlet fruits of a bitter-sweet taste. It and many other species are now growing in the United States, as a result of his exploration. (Figure 5.)

the descent was at times even dangerous and, horses and men all being tired, we camped at 4 P. M. on a grassy, level place, near a stream, and had a great time in getting enough to eat, for there are very few people in this elevated region of Central Asia and food is scarce and at times altogether unobtainable. We got, however, sour milk and pea-flour bread and, with some conserved sausages which we had still with us, we made a meal of it. The interpreter could not stand the rarefied mountain air; he had heavy hemorrhages from the nose twice a day and felt quite weak. The guide, who was addicted to strong drink, could not get anything, of course, and had become very sullen, so you may imagine that I was not in a sociable company.

Well, on Monday, July 11, we passed

through wild, rocky scenery, going along precipices where the horses had to be held by two men, one at the head and one at the tail, so as to prevent accidents. In the afternoon, about five o'clock, while collecting wild cherries on the mountain slope, we came all of a sudden upon a caravan, consisting of 20 people and still more horses. It proved to be the civil-administrator of the district, accompanied by the chief of police of Pendshikent, an interpreter, local chiefs of villages, guards, scouts, etc.

Our meeting was somewhat remarkable, as few white men ever travel in these regions.

The first thing we were asked for was, of course, our passports. The administrator (a Russian police-officer of high rank) said that my papers were not as they ought to be, as they were not defi-

SPIRAEA HYPERICIFOLIA.

One of the most ornamental wild shrubs of Asiatic Russia, found from the Caucasus region and Persia eastward to Mongolia and the region of Lake Baikal. It is able to stand great heat and drought and is therefore recommended as an ornamental park and garden shrub in the more arid sections of the United States. The above photograph was taken on a hillside near Tiflis, Caucasus, Russia, April 24, 1910. (Figure 6.)

nite enough, but I told him I had received them so from the acting chief of police in Pendshikent. Well, he let us go on. Half an hour later, however, a messenger came to us, informing us that we had to return, as the administrator did not feel he could let us go on any further. The acting chief of police in Pendshikent had made a failure of the document that he gave me, having forgotten to mention the exact date and number of my permission from St. Petersburg and he (the civil administrator), being held responsible for the district I was travelling in, could, under those circumstances, not allow me to go on any further.

RETURN NECESSARY.

He said he would allow me to stay there in this village, until a messenger had arrived from Samarkand, as he would investigate this affair; if things were found to be O. K., I could proceed farther on; if not, I would have to return under guard. I had a short conference with my men and then told this administrator that as it might take a messenger to and from Samarkand from five to ten or even twelve days before I could have been cleared of his suspicions, and as my caravan alone cost me from fifteen to twenty roubles a day, I had to decline his offer, but wanted to return by another road to Samarkand

THE PARADISE APPLE AT HOME.

This bushy apple (*Malus paradisiaca*), apparently a native of the Caucasus, is now widely grown all over the world as a grafting stock for dwarfing apples. Mr. Meyer believes it has still a useful future before it as a factor in producing a strain of bush apples suited especially to regions where the summer temperatures are too high for ordinary apples. Photograph made at Geok-Tapa, Caucasus, Russia, April 11, 1910. (Figure 7.)

and investigate this matter myself and find out who was responsible for this mishap. Well, he was kind enough to allow this and as I promised him I would not escape, I didn't even get any guard sent with me.

And so we left that village of Peki on Tuesday, July 12, 1910, went for the whole day along an extremely bad road where often the path went simply over sticks and poles, put slantingly in the rocks and covered over with brush and dirt. We wound along the roaring Zarafshan river, sometimes level with the water, then again several hundred feet above it. Tales of accidents had made us apprehensive of the great dangers of this road, but, thank Heaven,

nothing occurred save that the baggage looked less respectable in the evening than it had done at the outset. We had to employ three porters at the most dangerous points to carry the more valuable baggage, for it was too unsafe to allow it to remain on the packhorses' backs, especially my satchel, in which all passports and valuable papers are stored. If, for instance, my letter of credit, together with the passports, had gotten down in the deep, I could almost as well have shot myself, the more so as 1,000 roubles in paper money was also among its contents. It is my policy to have all my valuable belongings in only one receptacle, which has to be strong, not to be too heavy to be carried easily

by one person, but also not to be so light that one can easily run away with it; and this piece of baggage always has to be taken care of the very first thing and is always at night at my own head. Well, we passed this road, which is one of the worst I have seen in my life, safe and sound, and slept that night beneath old apricot trees in the court of a local dignitary in the prosperous town of Orono, situated in the rich valley of the Zarafshan.

WILD VEGETATION SCARCE.

On Wednesday, July 13, we followed the Zarafshan the whole day and passed several villages, where orchards of apricots, mulberries and walnuts intermingled. Wild vegetation, however, is almost absent. In a naturally dry climate, the long occupation of men has exterminated what little there formerly grew upon the mountain slopes and in the glens and today everything is scorched and barren.

On Thursday, July 14, we left the town of Langar, where we had stopped for the night, and passed through a region where almost no level spot was found at all; everywhere mountains and precipices, all rock and cliffs. As a result no villages have been established, and as distances are too long for peasants to carry away woody vegetation to their homes, we found lots of interesting plants: Pistaches, almonds in three species, *Prunus divaricata*, maples, junipers, coluteas, etc. In the herbarium material I sent off a few weeks ago, you'll find many labels bearing the date July 14, 1910. As I had to do all the collecting myself, my men not being intelligent enough for it, I was rather tired that day and was glad to sleep again on the porch of a Muhammadan mosque, notwithstanding a strong wind blew all night through the tall walnut trees and made one dream of storms at sea and fights in forests.

Friday, July 15, saw us leave Wishist, and late in the afternoon we came back again in Pendshikent, where our early return caused lots of surprise, since we had said we would stay out at least one month. And now we went to the police again and found out my name had been booked, but that the acting chief of

police was at fault. Then the horsemen to whom I had paid 100 roubles in advance, besides having lent them money on the road, wouldn't return the money and we had to ask the assistance of the police and a judge to get most of it back; even at that I lost twelve roubles on the transaction, besides finding it an extremely unpleasant business which lasted all through Friday evening and Saturday, July 16. The guide, to whom I had given some money, too, got dead drunk and made troubles worse. Yes, this whole trip was tragi-comical! It is good that I am sufficiently hardened off to stand a wee bit of trouble, otherwise such matters are able to make one lose temper and sense.

SECOND DEPARTURE.

On Sunday, July 17, we left Pendshikent again by cart and after a long day's ride we arrived in Samarkand at nine p. m.

On Tuesday next I went to the governor of Samarkand and complained verbally about this treatment I had experienced at the hands of his subordinates. He was a very kind man, had investigations made straightway, and in less than an hour I had a paper in my possession giving me full rights to travel in the same district from which I had been chased out. The very administrator who had been so suspicious, was smiles all over, and pointed out places on the map where many plants were found, and even offered to collect material. And there the matter rests.

When in Samarkand, my interpreter in the meantime had found out that certain things had been taken from his dwelling, while he was absent, and he made this as an excuse for not being willing to go any longer with me, although I knew that it was the hardships and the want of the "flesh pots of Egypt" that made him stay back. He promised, however, to accompany me to Tashkent and find me another interpreter, but after having had private troubles at home, he did not want to do that either, and left me wholly alone. Now I could have gone to the police and forced him to stay with me, as I had a witness that I had engaged him for at

DESERT POPLAR OF TURKESTAN.

A species (*Populus pruinosa*) which is widespread and extremely hardy in Turkestan. It is mixed with tamarisks, which are the low shrubs in the photograph. It also grows widely side by side with *Populus euphratica*, which it considerably resembles. It is one of the most recommended drought-resistant trees for arid regions with scorching summers and mild winters; needs almost no water; but is, unfortunately, difficult to propagate. The wood is hard and durable. (Figure 8.)

least one month, but I had in mind an old Dutch saying: "Mit onwillige honden is't slecht hazen vangen" ('tis a bad job catching hares with unwilling dogs), and in my work especially, if people don't put a little sympathy into it, one gets almost nothing accomplished at all.

AT THE RAILWAY TERMINUS.

ANDISHAN, TURKESTAN, RUSSIA,

Oct. 4, 1910.

As you see, I am now at the terminus of the Central Asian Railway, and will write you from here a short report of what passed over our heads these last weeks. We changed our plans and instead of going alone on Monday, with a Chinese interpreter, and taking the train, we hired a wagon and went on Tuesday, September 20, 1910. The reasons for going by wagon were many. Firstly, I have an awful amount of baggage (close upon 1,200 lbs.), which is very inconvenient to ship by rail, the more so as some of it is not accepted by the railroad unless crated, and that is too much work; secondly, my interpreter is a new man, whom I know only slightly, and there is no better chance of learning a fellow's characteristics than by subjecting him to a roughing trip; for the Chinese interpreter it was also not bad to learn how to travel in Russian Turkestan. Then in addition came the fact that I could study the country better by cart than from a train window, and last, not least, my health hadn't been of the best in Tashkent, and such a cart trip would make me all right again.

Well, all things went as well as they could. In three days' time we covered the distance from Tashkent to Khodjent, passed through rice fields, fruit gardens, deserts, etc. It is exceedingly difficult, however, to inspect fruit or vegetable gardens close by, as all the plantations are surrounded with high mud walls and strangers are not admitted. Then we also had difficulties in obtaining sufficient food in daytime, as Ramadhan, the Muhammadan month of fasting, was in progress. This incomprehensible religious feast allows no Mussulman to partake of food and drink

as long as the sun is in the skies. As soon, however, as that body sinks down, then eating and drinking commences and merriment is made until the break of day. The main meal is eaten then between eleven p. m. and one a. m. What use this unhealthy rule has is as yet a puzzle to me, but this is certain, that it is most inconvenient to all travelers and even to the believers themselves. We often couldn't get a cup of tea, even in daytime, and ready food was quite out of the question.

PEACHES UNDISCOVERABLE.

On Friday, September 23, we stayed in Khodjent and wanted to find some famous peach varieties. We were, however, unable to find anybody willing or capable to show us around, and it was a Muhammadan holiday besides, so we had to give it up. Our wagon driver had become dissatisfied with the expensiveness of feed for his horses and wanted an extraordinary price before he would go any further, although we had engaged him for at least as far as Kokand. Well, we wouldn't give in, and engaged two local two-wheeled carts and left the next morning, September 24. On Monday, September 26, we landed at sunset in Kokand and had our first clean-up in seven days. The last three days we had passed most of the time through sandy, stony and alkaline deserts, going sometimes axle deep in dust, so we and the baggage were simply covered with gray and brown coats of desert dust. At the Russian hotels we tried to find accommodation; they were suspicious of us and we had some trouble of getting a roof above our heads. We had to give our passports the very first thing, apparently to satisfy the fear that we were robbers, returning with loot!

In Kokand we stayed two days, inspected bazar, seed and grain market and looked over the fruits. Kokand is reputed to be the finest market in Central Asia, and I really expected to find many new things. There is, however, not as much in our line as one might wish to see. I got some samples of unusual varieties of almonds and a large brown chickpea which I had not seen before. There were also very fine speci-

WILD DESERT PEONY.

Unidentified species having medium large, carmine flowers and glossy, gracefully cut foliage of a dark green color; found growing on rather stony and sterile places in Turkestan. Sent to the United States by Meyer as a spring flowering plant for gardens and parks in the northern United States. (Figure 9.)

mens of pomegranates to be seen; that is, of fine color and size, but of very sour taste. Of grapes, the beautiful rosy-white *Ghusaine* table grape was very fine with its long, translucent berries, which taste remarkably sweet. .

In the immediate neighborhood of Kokand one sees field after field covered with cotton, alternated with alfalfa and "jugara." This last can stand considerable alkali and may be of some value in alkaline regions with long and hot summers. One also notes the masses of Oleaster trees that are everywhere around the fields and along watercourses. These Eleagnus trees exhibit a remarkable variation in general habitus, productivity and sizes of fruits. The bigger part of them all seem to be seedlings, and are planted apparently only as shelter material; at least the fruits of many are too astringent to be edible, and even of the larger fruited forms, only here and there are the fruits collected. It is, however, a beautiful tree in the landscape, especially the silvery-white forms with the narrow, long leaves.

CHOLERA ENCOUNTERED.

On Thursday, September 29, we left Kokand by train, after having packed our baggage so that the railroad could accept it. In the afternoon we arrived in Margelan, a town where the governor of the Ferghana Province resides. (The name Margelan was changed last year into that of Skobelev, but men persist yet in calling it by the old name, although the native city of Margelan, where only Sart people live, still retains its old name.)

We left Margelan in the afternoon of October 1, and arrived at evening in Andishan, where I have been writing these last days. We saw the police, of course, or rather were requested to come, and as *my* papers are in good shape, the German interpreter is allowed for the present to stay too, but we had to whisk our Chinaman away to some native inn, where he keeps company with a few fellow countrymen and eats with them. There is much cholera here in this place, and we are very careful with our food. Yesterday I believe

AN ORNAMENTAL EREMURUS.

Unidentified species from Kulikalan, province of Samarkand, Russian Turkestan. Its spikes of rosy pink flowers often reach a height of four feet. The plant is found at an altitude of 7,000 feet in rich, black soil, and is able to stand both drought and cold. (Figure 10.)

seventeen people died here from this dreadful disease, but in fact there may die many more, for the fanatical Muhammadan population persists in hiding cases of sickness and drinks water from polluted places as if there were not such things as bacilli. The summer lasts very long here. All the trees are still in full leaf, and where some have fallen, it is not from cold, but from drought. I hope we'll soon get a cold spell, so that I can send some scions and cuttings of various things.

My present interpreter is not a genius, but I'll see how we can plod along. Turkestan certainly is an extremely diffi-

cult country to move about in; the moment one leaves the railroad questions are being asked, and for every little excursion special permits are necessary. I wouldn't advise any one to select this land for a holiday trip, and I have to restrain myself not to leave this whole territory as it is and live somewhere in more peaceful surroundings.

Well, one or two more days and I'll leave by cart for Osh, from there by packhorses to Kashgar. Some robbers are reported to be on the road, and they murdered some people here these last two nights, but a botanical collector is generally exempted from those annoyances.

New Publications

PRODUCTIVE HORSE HUSBANDRY, by Carl W. Gay. Philadelphia and London, J. B. Lippincott & Company, 1914. Pp. xv. + 331, \$1.50.

Professor Gay of the University of Pennsylvania states that his purpose in writing this volume was "to emphasize *industry* as applied to horses." His treatment of the principles of breeding is, therefore, summary and wholly practical. The book should be of value to anyone taking up horse breeding as a business.

THE CULTURE OF BLACK AND SILVER FOXES, by R. B. and L. V. Croft. Woodstock, the Rod and Gun Press, 1913. Pp. 83, 60 cents.

This is the latest handboók produced by the amazingly rapid development of silver fox breeding on Prince Edward Island, and is destined for those taking up the work as a money-making proposition. Hence it is primarily of practical nature, but the authors have inserted a considerable amount of theoretical discussion of heredity. They consider the silver fox the product of variation and isolation, not of hybridization, and declare that the coat color is never blended in inheritance, but either "particulate" or "exclusive." Their data, however, show that many factors must be concerned, and they admit that no systematic experiments have been undertaken to discover the ancestry of the present valuable breeds of foxes.

The Immigration Problem

We have an opportunity which is unique in history for the practice of eugenic principles, immediately and on a vastly greater scale than is possible in the case of any other nation. By selecting our immigrants, through proper legislation, we can pick out the best specimens of each race to be our fellow-citizens, and to be the parents of our future citizens. The responsibility which rests upon us in this matter is overwhelming.—Robert DeC. Ward: *The Crisis in our Immigration Policy* (Inst. Quart. Ill., IV, 2, 1913).